

Model Complexity as a Mitigation Strategy Against Industrial Espionage through Membership Inference Attacks

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Abstract—Machine learning (ML) models, particularly in the context of Federated Learning (FL), are increasingly used to enable predictive maintenance in smart industry. However, as these models become integral to industrial operations, they also become potential targets for data leakage and membership inference attacks (MIAs). In this paper, we hypothesise that training on multi-dimensional data (i.e., multiple features instead of a single feature) enhances resilience against MIAs compared to simpler, single-feature models. To test this hypothesis, we design an experimental testbed to empirically evaluate the vulnerability of ML models to black-box MIAs. Our approach involves training models of varying complexity on industrial time-series data and measuring their vulnerability to MIAs. Additionally, we introduce a human expert’s perspective to contextualise our findings in the realm of industrial espionage, emphasising the real-world implications of data leakage risks. Our results provide insights into the trade-offs between security, model complexity, and computational cost, offering practical guidance for practitioners seeking to deploy FL-based predictive maintenance solutions while minimising privacy risks.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Membership Inference Attack, Predictive Maintenance, Industrial Espionage

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid adoption of smart technologies and AI-driven solutions in industrial settings has transformed the operational landscapes of manufacturing and production. A cornerstone of this transformation is the integration of predictive maintenance systems, which utilise real-time data to anticipate potential machinery failures and optimise performance. To achieve this, many smart machinery vendors have embraced Federated Learning (FL) as a means to develop and deploy machine learning (ML) models. FL allows the aggregation of model updates from multiple distributed sources without transferring sensitive raw data, thereby addressing privacy concerns and fostering collaborative innovation.

However, despite its promise, FL is not immune to privacy and security risks. One emerging and largely overlooked threat in this context is the potential for industrial espionage facilitated by the FL framework. Consider a scenario where a smart machinery vendor supplies identical AI-enabled machines to two competing factories, referred to here as **Company A** and **Company B**. These machines collect run-time metrics, such as vibration, torque, and temperature, to locally train models for predictive maintenance. The vendor then aggregates these

model updates to refine a global model, which is shared back with the companies. The vendor claims that this approach ensures that no sensitive operational data leaves the premises of either company, seemingly protecting their proprietary information.

However, models trained via FL are known to be vulnerable to attacks such as membership inference (MIA) [1], where an adversary can deduce whether specific data points were part of the training process. This vulnerability raises serious concerns in the context of industrial operations. In this scenario, Company A, through a targeted effort, could potentially infer details about Company B’s runtime metrics and machinery states. With sufficient domain expertise, even seemingly innocent data can reveal critical insights into Company B’s operational strategies, machinery robustness, and overall business processes. Such intelligence can provide Company A with a significant competitive advantage, blurring the lines between legitimate collaboration and industrial espionage.

The implications of this vulnerability are particularly severe in industries relying on heavy machinery, where operational metrics are tightly coupled with productivity, cost-efficiency, and market competitiveness. A small breach in data privacy can cascade into a substantial compromise of business secrets [2]. Despite these risks, the current discourse on FL in industrial settings mostly emphasises its benefits, often neglecting the nuanced opportunities it creates for malicious actors.

This paper aims to address this gap by exploring how the FL paradigm, while designed to safeguard data privacy, inadvertently opens avenues for industrial espionage. By analysing the specific vulnerabilities inherent in the FL setup used for predictive maintenance, we highlight the risks posed to competing enterprises sharing a common vendor. Furthermore, we discuss the broader implications of these risks on industrial competitiveness and propose countermeasures to mitigate such threats. In doing so, this work seeks to inform both the cybersecurity community and industrial stakeholders about the emerging challenges and responsibilities in deploying FL-based solutions in high-stakes environments.

As its main contribution, this paper aims to answer the following two research questions (RQs): **RQ1** – To what extent are ML models used for anomaly detection in predictive maintenance vulnerable to MIAs, whether trained in

a centralised or federated manner? **RQ2** – Does increasing model complexity (e.g., using multi-feature data instead of single-feature data, or multi-class classification instead of binary classification) improve resilience against MIAs? We answer these questions by conducting a series of empirical experimental evaluations and providing an expert’s view on the topic from the perspective of industrial espionage.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. Section II briefs the reader on the topics of ML-driven predictive maintenance and the existing data leakage challenge. Section III proposes a mitigation hypothesis which we further aim to prove in Section IV with a series of experiments. Section V then proceeds with a discussion revisiting the initially posed RQs. Section VI concludes the paper with final remarks and an outlook for future work.

II. RESEARCH CONTEXT

A. ML-Driven Predictive Maintenance in Smart Factories

The smart factory represents a major evolution in manufacturing, integrating advanced sensors, IoT devices, and AI-driven systems to create a highly automated, data-driven production environment. These factories leverage real-time operational data to optimise efficiency, minimise downtime, and enhance product quality through continuous monitoring and predictive analytics. A key enabler of predictive maintenance in smart factories is ML, which analyses sensor data to detect patterns indicative of potential failures. Among various ML paradigms, supervised learning is the most widely adopted approach, as it enables models to learn from historically labelled datasets and accurately identify known failure modes [3]. By training on labelled examples of normal and faulty conditions, supervised models can classify operational states with high accuracy, making them particularly useful for fault detection, failure prediction, and early anomaly detection.

Since manufacturing environments produce vast amounts of time-series data, such as vibration signals, temperature fluctuations, torque measurements, and energy consumption metrics, supervised models are often designed to process sequential inputs [4]. Techniques such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are commonly used to capture temporal dependencies in sensor readings [5], allowing for more reliable failure prediction. Accurately analysing these historical trends helps factories anticipate breakdowns before they occur, thus enabling proactive maintenance strategies that reduce costs and improve overall equipment efficiency. Alongside these ML methods, FL is gaining traction as a privacy-preserving alternative to traditional centralised learning [6], [7]. FL enables multiple organisations to collaboratively train models without sharing sensitive raw data [8]. This approach is especially beneficial in industries with strict data privacy constraints, such as healthcare, finance, and manufacturing, where operational metrics must remain confidential [9]. By aggregating model updates instead of raw data, FL aims to comply with privacy regulations while facilitating knowledge sharing and innovation across organisations.

Role of Human Expertise: While ML-driven AI play a critical role in automating anomaly detection and predictive maintenance, the complexity and variability of industrial operations still requires the involvement of human domain experts. These experts possess the contextual knowledge required to interpret subtle signals from multiple data streams, such as vibration fluctuations coupled with slight temperature changes, and diagnose underlying issues. Their ability to synthesise fragmented information and make informed decisions remains central to the reliability and efficiency of smart factory operations. Furthermore, the human experts play the central role in labelling the collected training data – a key pre-requisite for efficient supervised learning.

The interplay between machine intelligence and human expertise highlights the importance of preserving the integrity and privacy of operational data. Even a small glimpse into a competitor’s data streams, if analysed by a skilled domain expert, could unveil critical insights about their operations and strategies. This highlights the need for robust safeguards in FL frameworks to prevent unintended disclosures in collaborative industrial settings.

B. Data Leakage through Membership Inference Attacks

The adoption of FL in smart factory environments is driven by the need to preserve data privacy while leveraging AI-driven predictive maintenance. However, while FL avoids direct data exposure, research has demonstrated that even compiled models can still leak sensitive information about their training data [10]. This vulnerability is particularly concerning in industrial settings, where proprietary sensor data, machine performance indicators, and operational trends could be exploited by competitors or malicious actors.

Among various privacy attacks [11], MIAs pose a considerable risk to the smart factory domain. MIAs allow an adversary to determine whether a specific data point was used in the training set, which can have severe implications in predictive maintenance. For instance, if a competitor infers that a rival company’s model was trained on data indicative of machine failures or excessive wear, they could deduce weaknesses in their production processes, supply chain issues, or maintenance inefficiencies, potentially gaining an unfair strategic advantage. MIAs have been demonstrated on both centralised models and federated models. In centralised learning, an attacker can exploit a single globally trained model, while in federated setups, even though raw data is never directly shared, model updates still encode patterns that can be leveraged for inference.

In this paper, we will specifically focus on black-box MIAs, first introduced by Shokri et al. [12], which assume that the adversary does not have direct access to the target model’s internal parameters but can query it and observe its output probabilities. These attacks rely on the fact that a model often behaves differently for data it has seen during training, revealing membership information via variations in confidence scores. The attack follows a three-step process [13]:

1) **Shadow Model Training:** The attacker trains multiple shadow models to mimic the behaviour of the target model. These shadow models are trained on separate datasets, designed to approximate the distribution of the real training data. The key assumption is that if the target model is trained on proprietary machine sensor data, an attacker might have access to a similar available dataset (e.g., retrieved from own factory).

2) **Attack Model Construction:** After training the shadow models, the attacker collects their outputs (i.e., confidence scores for different classes) on samples known to be in the training set and samples that were not. These outputs serve as features to train a new attack classifier that learns to distinguish between in-training and out-of-training samples.

3) **Inference on the Target Model:** The attack model is then applied to the real target model. By feeding new data samples and observing the model’s probability outputs, the attack model predicts if a given sample was part of the target model’s original training set. A successful attack would allow an adversary to infer the presence of specific machine operational states, sensor anomalies, or failure conditions during training.

This attack is particularly effective when the target model is overconfident in predicting training samples, leading to distributional differences between in-sample and out-of-sample confidence scores. In FL, while direct data access is restricted, updates still encode feature relevance and training set information, making them vulnerable to gradient-based or prediction-based MIAs. A key metric to quantify the effectiveness of MIAs, both in centralised and federated setups, is **attack accuracy**, which measures how often the MIA correctly identifies whether a sample was part of the training set. It is defined as:

$$\text{Attack Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}, \text{ where:}$$

- *TP* (True Positive): The attack correctly predicts that a training sample was used in training.
- *TN* (True Negative): The attack correctly predicts that a non-training sample was not in the training set.
- *FP* (False Positive): The attack incorrectly predicts that a non-training sample was part of the training set.
- *FN* (False Negative): The attack incorrectly predicts that a training sample was not in the training set.

Implications for Industrial Espionage: In more practical terms, an attack accuracy significantly above 50% suggests that the model is leaking information about its training set. A random guess would yield 50% accuracy, meaning a high accuracy indicates a strong privacy vulnerability. In an industrial context, even a small fragment of leaked data, for example, an inferred run-time metric or operational trend, can be highly revealing when analysed by a domain expert. A knowledgeable professional with experience in the field can cross-reference these leaks with existing operational knowledge and deduce key aspects of a competitor’s strategies, machinery health, or process efficiencies. This ability to draw actionable insights from incomplete or uncertain data increases the economic threat posed by ML model vulnerabilities. For example:

- **Production Trends:** Inferred anomalies or operational bottlenecks can provide a competitor with insights into peak loads or maintenance cycles.
- **Machinery Robustness:** Identified patterns may expose weaknesses or over-utilised components, offering a competitive advantage in pricing or strategy.
- **Process Optimisation:** Reverse-engineering operational setups from leaked metrics can lead to replication or counter-strategies that undercut competitive advantages.

Thus, even without complete certainty, a combination of ML models’ privacy flaws and human domain expertise can transform minor data leaks into considerable strategic advantages.

III. HYPOTHESIS: THE ROLE OF MODEL COMPLEXITY IN MITIGATING MEMBERSHIP INFERENCE RISKS

In this study, we hypothesise that adopting a more complex ML approach for anomaly detection in predictive maintenance provides better resilience against MIAs, which are critical concerns in the context of data leakage and industrial espionage. We argue that a system trained on multi-dimensional datasets is inherently more resilient to such attacks than a simpler system based on multiple binary classifiers trained on individual time-series data streams. More specifically, **Approach 1** involves using multiple independent binary classifiers, where each classifier is trained on a single time-series data stream with a single labelled feature (e.g., vibration, torque, or temperature). These classifiers perform anomaly detection by labelling the observed data as either **normal operation** or **anomaly**. The system does not integrate information across the streams – instead, the task of diagnosing the root cause of anomalies across multiple features is left to a human domain expert. The expert manually correlates anomalies detected across individual streams and uses their knowledge of the machinery and industrial processes to draw conclusions about potential failures or issues. **Approach 2**, on the other hand, aggregates the individual time-series data streams into a unified, multi-dimensional dataset containing multiple features recorded simultaneously. A single, more complex classification model is trained on this combined dataset. By doing so, it encapsulates the diagnostic knowledge of the human expert directly into the model, enabling automated correlation and diagnosis across multiple data streams.

Our hypothesis is based on the following reasoning:

- 1) **Data representation in complex models:** The second approach aggregates multiple features across time-series streams into a unified multi-dimensional dataset. This results in a model that learns complex interdependencies and patterns, encoding the relationships between features in latent representations. These representations obscure the original data points, making it harder for adversaries to infer sensitive information from model updates.
- 2) **Attack Difficulty:** MIAs typically exploit the model’s behaviour on specific inputs to detect over-fitting or reconstruct training data. In Approach 1, where models are simpler and isolated, the link between input and model behaviour is more direct, making them more vulnerable. In contrast, the more

complex model of Approach 2 with non-linear transformations and inter-feature dependencies increases the complexity of attack methods needed to extract meaningful information.

3) **Human Expert’s Role:** In Approach 1, the reliance on humans to correlate anomalies across features leaves the system vulnerable to indirect inference attacks. An adversary with partial data and domain expertise can leverage reconstructed individual anomalies to make educated guesses about a competitor’s operations. In Approach 2, the encapsulation of expert knowledge into the model reduces this reliance, limiting the potential for adversarial use of leaked information.

To prove this hypothesis, we will conduct a series of experiments, anticipating that Approach 2 will demonstrate lower vulnerability to MIAs compared to Approach 1. While Approach 2 introduces additional complexity in training and implementation, the increased resilience to data leakage and adversarial inference will outweigh these costs, especially in industrial domains where the stakes of data privacy and competitive advantage are high. The results of these experiments will provide critical insights into the trade-offs between simplicity and security in designing ML-driven predictive maintenance systems and offer guidance for industries looking to safeguard their operational data against emerging threats.

IV. PROOF OF CONCEPT

A. Experiment Design to Prove the Hypothesis

TABLE I
FOUR EXPERIMENT SETUPS FOR EMPIRICAL EVALUATION.

	Single-feature data	Multi-feature data
Centralised training	Setup 1: in this setting, each time-series data stream (i.e., vibration along X, Y, or Z axes) is associated with an individual binary classifier trained to detect anomalies for that specific axis. These classifiers are relatively simple, with each trained on a single feature, and the task of correlating anomalies across features is delegated to a knowledgeable human expert.	Setup 2: an alternative approach involves training a more complex ML model capable of correlating anomalies across multiple time-series data streams. This model essentially encodes the knowledge and expertise of the human expert into its architecture and decision-making process, reducing reliance on manual interpretation.
Federated learning	Setup 3: this is similar to Setup 1, but the training process over single-feature data is distributed across multiple federated clients which train on their own subset and periodically share model updates with the central aggregator which produces a global model.	Setup 4: this is similar to Setup 3, but the training process over multi-feature data is distributed across multiple federated clients which train on their own subset and periodically share model updates with the central aggregator which produces a global model.

To evaluate this hypothesis, we will conduct a series of experiments simulating both approaches in centralised and federated settings and subjecting them to MIAs. More specifically, we will consider 4 experiment setups summarised in Table I. The experiments will follow these steps:

1) *Dataset Preparation:* In general, one of the biggest challenges in AI-driven predictive maintenance is the lack of publicly available real-world datasets. Due to the sensitive nature of industrial operations, companies are often reluctant to

publish machine sensor data, as it can expose proprietary information about their manufacturing processes, failure patterns, and maintenance strategies. This makes benchmarking privacy risks, such as MIAs, particularly difficult. The Bosch CNC Machining Dataset, introduced in [14], provides a valuable benchmark dataset for evaluating predictive maintenance models in a real industrial setting. The dataset contains acceleration data collected from three separate CNC milling machines over a two-year period in a real production plant. This makes it highly relevant for our study, as it allows us to explore both centralised and FL setups. Three key properties of this dataset make it a good fit for our research:

- **FL Simulation:** Three distinct CNC machines in the dataset can be used as separate federated clients, enabling a realistic re-construction of FL-based predictive maintenance.
- **Binary Classification Setup:** The dataset provides two labeled classes – **good** (normal operation) and **bad** (anomalous operation) – allowing us to train anomaly detection models for predictive maintenance.
- **Multi-Feature and Single-Feature Comparisons:** The dataset includes vibration data along three axes (X, Y, and Z). This enables us to train models using all three features together (multi-feature models) or train separate models for each axis individually (single-feature models).

2) *Model Training:* Using the dataset, we then trained a binary classification model using a CNN-LSTM architecture. This model was chosen for its ability to extract spatial features from vibration signals through convolutional layers while also capturing temporal dependencies using recurrent layers [15]. The goal was to distinguish between good and bad operation based on the recorded vibration data. Despite implementing different training setups, we aimed to minimise variations across experiments to ensure a fair comparison with minimal assumptions. The training procedure was kept as consistent as possible, with the primary difference being the learning paradigm – centralised vs. federated. One key assumption in our comparison was the number of training epochs. For centralised training, models were trained for 100 epochs on the entire dataset. In the FL setup, training was conducted over 10 communication rounds, with each federated client running 10 local epochs per round before sending model updates to the central aggregator. This setup ensured that the total training effort across centralised and federated setups remained comparable, preventing significant biases in convergence due to differing amounts of training.

Each model was trained using the same optimiser, learning rate, and batch size, ensuring that performance differences primarily come from the training approach rather than hyperparameter variations. In FL, client updates were aggregated using Federated Averaging (FedAvg) [16], maintaining consistency across different machines without introducing additional optimisation techniques that could skew results. Additionally, the same train-test splits were applied in all setups to further control for variability in data distribution. By structuring the training process in this way, we aimed to ensure that

any observed differences in model performance or privacy vulnerabilities were attributable to the learning paradigm itself rather than extraneous factors.

3) *Simulated Membership Inference Attacks*: We then conducted simulated MIAs following the black-box attack methodology introduced by Shokri et al. [12]. The objective was to determine whether an adversary could infer if a specific data point was part of the training set based solely on the model’s output probabilities. By analysing how vulnerable different models were to MIAs, we aimed to evaluate whether training on multi-feature vs. single-feature data and centralised vs. federated training affected privacy vulnerabilities. Despite implementing different attack scenarios, the MIA setup remained consistent across all experiments to maintain a fair comparison. Each attack followed the same methodology, beginning with the construction of shadow models that were trained on datasets similar to those used for the target model. These shadow models mimicked the behaviour of the target model and were used to generate synthetic data points labelled as **in** (samples that were part of the training set) or **out** (samples that were not). Using these labelled samples, an attack model was trained to distinguish between training and non-training samples based on the confidence scores produced by the target model.

The same attack model architecture, optimiser, and hyper-parameters were applied across all experiments to ensure that any observed differences in attack success rates were a direct result of the underlying training setup rather than variations in attack methodology. In FL setups, the attack was conducted on the final aggregated global model, simulating a realistic scenario where an external adversary attempts to infer training set membership without access to individual client updates. In all setups, attack effectiveness was measured using its accuracy calculated as described in Section II.

B. Experimental Results and Main Observations

Table II summarises the results of the experiments. In all experiments but one, the accuracy of the classification models was above 90% which is commonly considered acceptable given the involvement of a human expert responsible for the final decision. At the same time, the resilience of the trained models to MIAs varied across the setups considerably, yielding higher accuracy in the single-feature models compared to the multi-feature models. This difference is highlighted in the bar chart in Figure 1.

MIAs are more effective in the single-feature scenarios due to the simplicity of the models. Each classifier focuses on a single feature, making it easier to reconstruct training data. The attack essentially isolates and targets individual feature distributions, simplifying the reverse engineering process. A more complex model handling multi-feature data, although still vulnerable, introduces challenges for MIAs. These models aggregate and transform raw feature data into latent representations, embedding relationships between features in higher-dimensional spaces. Attacks would need to reverse-engineer these complex latent representations to reconstruct meaningful

training data, which is computationally and methodologically more challenging. Furthermore, the interplay between features dilutes the influence of any single feature, potentially reducing the granularity of the reconstructed data.

One notable exception is the experiment on the Y-axis data in the centralised setup, which produced lower model accuracy. A possible explanation is that the Y-axis vibrations may have low correlation with anomalies. If the Y-axis measurements alone do not contain strong predictive patterns, then a model trained solely on this data in a centralised manner would struggle to generalise, explaining the low accuracy of 58%. Noteworthy, the MIA accuracy in this case is also low (20%) – arguably, because the model struggled with learning meaningful patterns which could then be extracted by the attack.

At the same time, it is also quite possible that the Y-axis vibration patterns differ significantly across the three machines due to differences in machine structure, alignment, or load conditions. If this is the case, when training centrally, the model is exposed to high variability in Y-axis features, which makes learning a generalisable decision boundary difficult. The model may be overfitting to specific machine behaviours rather than learning a general pattern of normal vs. abnormal operation. In contrast, in the FL setup, each local model is trained only on its respective machine’s data, so it learns meaningful patterns for that specific machine without interference from the others. When the global model aggregates the local models, it benefits from the specialised knowledge from each machine while smoothing out inconsistencies across different data distributions.

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF MODEL UTILITY (ANOMALY DETECTION ACCURACY)
AND PRIVACY (MIA RESILIENCE).

Setup		Model Accuracy (%)	MIA Accuracy (%)
Centralised Single-Feature	X-axis	93%	79.97%
	Y-axis	58%	20.03%
	Z-axis	94%	79.97%
Centralised Multi-Feature		90%	68.27%
Federated Single-Feature	X-axis	95.41%	81.24%
	Y-axis	95.41%	77.80%
	Z-axis	95.41%	80.05%
Federated Multi-Feature		94.89%	64.47%

V. DISCUSSION

Answering RQ1: Our experimental results demonstrate that all models, regardless of training setup, exhibit some degree of vulnerability to MIAs. Both centralised and FL approaches were vulnerable, with attack success rates significantly higher than random guessing, confirming that training data membership can be inferred with non-trivial accuracy. However, the extent of vulnerability varied depending on model architecture, training setup, and data representation.

In centralised training, models trained on single-feature data were highly vulnerable to MIAs due to their tendency to overfit to specific patterns within the dataset. In FL, the global model aggregated across multiple clients also showed vulnerability to

Fig. 1. MIA accuracy across different training scenarios.

MIAs. This highlights an existing limitation of FL – i.e. while it prevents direct data sharing, it does not inherently prevent privacy leakage through model updates. However, federated models trained on diverse client data distributions tended to generalise better, making them slightly more resistant to MIAs than their centralised counterparts.

The key take-away from RQ1 is that neither centralised nor federated models provide protection against MIAs. Therefore, additional privacy-preserving techniques, such as differential privacy, adversarial training, or regularisation strategies [17], are required to mitigate these risks.

Answering RQ2: Our experiments indicate that increasing model complexity by using multi-feature data improves resilience to MIAs. Models trained on combined X, Y, and Z-axis vibration data consistently exhibited lower attack success rates compared to those trained on single-axis data. This suggests that higher-dimensional feature spaces introduce more complex decision boundaries, making it harder for an attacker to distinguish between training and non-training samples based solely on confidence scores.

Interestingly, the performance gap between single-feature and multi-feature models was most evident in FL setups. This indicates that combining diverse feature inputs not only improves anomaly detection performance but also enhances privacy protection, particularly when data is distributed across multiple clients. The improved generalisation of multi-feature models likely reduces the over-confidence of the classifier, which is a key factor exploited in MIAs. While we did not experiment with multi-class classification, our findings suggest that further increasing model complexity in this way could offer additional privacy benefits. However, it remains an open question whether this effect generalises across different industrial datasets and attack methodologies. We see this as an interesting direction for further research.

The key take-away from RQ2 is that training on multi-feature data is a viable mitigation strategy against MIAs, as it improves both model accuracy and privacy protection. This insight is particularly relevant for predictive maintenance applications, where the choice of input features can significantly impact both performance and data security.

Implications of the research findings for industrial espionage: The presence of a domain expert significantly amplifies the risk of industrial espionage when ML models are vulnerable to MIAs. Even if only partial data is reconstructed through an attack, an expert can leverage domain-specific knowledge to derive meaningful operational insights about a competitor. A promising countermeasure is to embed expert knowledge directly into the model, making it more complex and abstract in how it correlates input features. This increases the difficulty for an adversary attempting to reconstruct meaningful insights from a successful MIA. Even if an attacker is able to infer some training data membership, they would still lack the context and internal correlation mechanisms that drive the model’s decision-making process. Without these, the extracted data remains fragmented and less actionable, diminishing its strategic value and reducing the risk of industrial espionage.

While increasing model complexity improves privacy protection, it introduces practical trade-offs that must be considered from an industrial AI practitioner’s perspective. First, complexity vs. interpretability is a major concern. More sophisticated models, such as those trained on multi-feature data, tend to be less interpretable, making it challenging to validate outputs, troubleshoot issues, or ensure regulatory compliance, particularly in safety-critical industrial applications. Second, adversaries may respond with more advanced attack techniques targeting high-dimensional, complex models. However, the effort, expertise, and computational resources required to launch such attacks increase significantly, making them far less practical and scalable compared to attacking simpler models. Finally, despite these defenses, a determined and knowledgeable adversary may still extract high-level operational insights from fragmented information. While the likelihood and precision of such inferences are reduced, the risk is never fully eliminated.

From a practitioner’s standpoint, ensuring strong data privacy measures remains the most critical factor in mitigating the risk of industrial espionage. While increasing model complexity offers additional protection, it should not be viewed as a standalone defense. The most effective way to eliminate risk is to prevent sensitive data exposure entirely, reinforcing the need for privacy-preserving techniques such as differential privacy, encryption, or secure aggregation in FL.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the vulnerability of ML models used for predictive maintenance in smart factories to MIAs. While FL is widely regarded as a privacy-preserving paradigm that enables collaborative model training without sharing raw data, our findings confirm that FL does not inherently prevent data leakage. Using black-box MIAs, specifically the method introduced by Shokri et al., we evaluated the vulnerability of both centralised and federated models to attacks that attempt to infer whether specific data points were used during training. Our experiments compared binary classification models trained on single-feature data (X, Y, or Z-axis vibrations) against those trained on multi-feature data (combining all three axes).

The results indicate that models trained on multi-feature data exhibited higher resilience to MIAs, likely due to more complex feature interactions and higher-dimensional decision boundaries, which make it harder for an attacker to distinguish training and non-training samples based on model accuracy.

These findings are particularly critical in the context of industrial espionage, where access to inferred information about a competitor's predictive maintenance models could provide insights into their machinery health, production efficiency, and operational strategies. A company that successfully applies MIAs against a competitor's model could determine which failure modes were most frequently encountered, revealing potential weaknesses in production processes or supply chain vulnerabilities. Such intelligence could be leveraged to gain a competitive edge, whether by improving internal operations or exploiting market weaknesses. Our results underscore the urgent need for stronger privacy defenses in industrial AI applications. While FL reduces direct data exposure, it remains vulnerable to MIAs, emphasising the need for privacy-enhancing mechanisms such as differential privacy, adversarial training, or regularisation techniques to mitigate information leakage. As predictive maintenance systems become more advanced, ensuring that models are not only accurate but also secure from inference attacks will be crucial in safeguarding proprietary industrial data from exploitation.

A. Future Work

In this study, we focused primarily on multi-feature data as a mitigation strategy against MIAs. However, another important research direction is to compare the robustness of multi-class classification models trained on multi-feature data against binary classification models trained on single-feature data. Since multi-class models inherently encode more complex decision boundaries, they may introduce additional privacy risks or, conversely, provide better generalisation, making them potentially more resistant to inference attacks. An empirical evaluation of this trade-off would further enhance our understanding of how data dimensionality and model complexity affect privacy vulnerabilities.

Additionally, a broader generalisation of our findings is necessary to assess whether the observed trends hold across diverse datasets and different MIA techniques. While we focused on black-box MIA, many other attack methodologies exist, including gradient inversion attacks, property inference attacks, and differential privacy-based exploits [13]. Evaluating these approaches on alternative industrial datasets would allow for a more comprehensive assessment of privacy risks in federated predictive maintenance models and inform the development of stronger defenses tailored to industrial AI applications.

Finally, an obvious extension to this work is the application of our methodology to real-world production data as part of an ongoing R&D project. While this has significant practical implications, particularly for evaluating the impact of MIAs in live industrial settings, the sensitive nature of proprietary manufacturing data may prevent the publication of specific

findings. This aligns with the data confidentiality concerns extensively discussed in this paper and underscores the broader challenge of balancing industrial AI research with corporate data protection policies.

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